
Theoretical Perspective of Change Management

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Abstract The purpose of this paper is to show different theoretical perspectives as far as change management is concerned. The flow of the paper is through the history to the current stage of the change management. Apart, different historical perspectives are covered into the same. The paper presents the synopsis of the various works done by different authors and consultants over the number of years and provides insights on how sustainable change is achieved to propel an entity towards business excellence. It is very much important to manager the change successfully and efficiently. These skills are crucial to acquire. If the same is not managed skilfully then it can result into the crisis. The paper also suggests on to how to manage the change effectively

Keywords Change management, managing change, sustainability

Introduction

Change management refers to any approach to transitioning individuals, teams, and organizations using methods intended to re-direct the use of resources, business process, budget allocations, or other modes of operation that significantly reshape a company or organization. Organizational change management (OCM) considers the full organization and what needs to change [1].

History of Change Management

S. No.	Year	Author	Development
1	1960	Everett Rogers	According to his work mentioned in “diffusion of innovations”, he suggested that change must be understood according to the time, different channel of communications and its impact on associated people [2]
2	1980	Robert Marshak	Came up with entire different process in terms of reengineering services for the change management process [3]
3	1982	Julien Phillips	Published a model of change management [4]
4	1993	Daryl Conner	In the book, “managing at the speed of change”, he came up with a term ‘Building Platform’, into which he focused on human performance & adoption techniques in terms of technological innovations [5]
5	2000	Linda Ackerman Anderson	created the role of the change leader to take responsibility & Accountability for the human side of the change [6]
6	2010	Christina Dean	Change management is now an established and formal vocation [7]
7	2016	The Association of Change Management Professionals	Announced a new certification to enhance the profession: Certified Change Management Professional [8]

Definition

The Change Management can be defined as a planned objective to change a company's direction from the current position to a desired future position in the business environment in response to new challenges and opportunities. It includes the projection of a new vision, together with wide consultation with employees at all levels to overcome resistance and gain the acceptance. It is also essential that the requisite leadership skills, commitment at all levels and both human and financial resources are available to implement the desired change.

Change Management: Behaviour & Action

S. No.	Behaviour	Action
1	Determine the need for change	Establish the objectives and processes
2	Prepare and Plan for Change	implement the plan, execute the process, make the product
3	Implement the Change	study actual results and compare against the expected results
4	Sustain the Change	Enact the new standards

John Kotter's 8-Step Process for Change Management

Dr. John Kotter, Professor of Harvard Business School, has come up with a process of Change Management consisting of eight steps [9].

1) Establish a Sense of Urgency

In this stage, the company has to examine the market and competitive realities to understand and implement the change. Apart from the same, identification of the different sort of crisis and major opportunities to overcome the same has to be analysed. Once, the same has been done, it is also essential to provide the evidence of the required change.

2) Create the Guiding Coalition

The group has to be assembled so that the change efforts can be put in more enthusiastically. Also, the commitment of the people is essential for the same. The company has to encourage people to work together as a group.

3) Develop a Vision and Strategy

The proper vision and well defined strategy can help to enforce change in a better manner.

4) Communicate the Change Vision

The change has to be aligned and communicated properly in order to achieve the desired results. The proper and transparent communication can be helpful to enhance the performance level and adaptability of the organization.

5) Empower Employees

The change can be enforced properly by empowering employees in proper manner. The obstacles are to be removed tactfully which are coming in a way of the progressive change. The collaboration and empowerment of the employees can be proven helpful for the same.

6) Generate Short-Term Wins

The short term goal achievement can boost up the morale of the employee in terms of change. The same can smoothen the process in terms of psychological aspect. Also, the rewards and recognition can improve the acceptance and receptivity level.

7) Do Not Let Up

The continuous improvement has to be a part of the change management process. The loop holes are to be eliminated immediately once the process has been implemented in full-fledged terms.

8) Make Change Stick

The same helps to Articulate the connections between the new behaviours and the corporate success.

Suggestions & Conclusion

This paper concludes that to manage & sustain the change, it is very much important that the employees should be communicated on the same part as far as change is concerned. All the areas of the newness should be communicated in a proper manner. Once the change has been implemented, the continuous evaluation has to be done. In short, change should be implanted in terms of proper policy making and implementation.

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